

Heliopolis Project

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Entry tags: Archaeological monument, Tomb, Graeco-Roman, Alexandria, Cemetery, City, Egypt, Greece, Hellenistic Religions, shrines, Altar, Sacred Enclosure, Temple, Constantine, Temenos, Religious Complex, Open-Air Sanctuary, Shrine, Monument, Religious Place, Islamic Traditions, Egyptian Religions, Aegean, Religious Group, Early Christianity

In 2012, the Heliopolis Project, our Egyptian-German joint venture project under the direction of Dr. Aiman Ashmawy (Egyptian Ministry of Tourism and Antiquities) and Prof. Dr. Dietrich Raue (University of Leipzig), started to excavate various areas of the site. As this is an ongoing project, our research is constantly increasing the general knowledge and information about Heliopolis, a major cult centre of Ancient Egypt. It is located in the modern suburb of Matariya northeast of Cairo. Heliopolis was active throughout the Pharaonic history of ancient Egypt, and dedicated in particular to the different manifestations of the solar gods, Khepri, Ra-Horakhty, and Atum, though there were also elements dedicated to aspects of Hathor and Osiris. This was an important cult centre also for festivals related to the jubilee festival of the king.

Date Range: 3500 BCE - 2021 CE

Region: Cairo

Region tags: Africa, Egypt

Matariya / Ancient Heliopolis / Cairo

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Saleh, Abdel-Aziz 1981/83. Excavations at Heliopolis. Ancient Egyptian Ounû. Vol. I/II (the site of Tell el-Hiṣn-Maṭarīyah). Cairo: Univ. Faculty of Archaeology
- Source 2: Petrie, W. M. Flinders and Ernest Mackay 1915. Heliopolis, Kafr Ammar and Shurafa. British School of Archaeology in Egypt and Egyptian Research Account [24] (18th year).
- Source 3: Raue, Dietrich 2020. Reise zum Ursprung der Welt: die Ausgrabungen im Tempel von Heliopolis. Unter Mitarbeit von Aiman Ashmawy. Darmstadt: wbg Philipp von Zabern

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <http://www.heliopolisproject.org/site-information/>
- Source 1 Description: The Heliopolis Project Website

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

↳ Type of excavation:

– Scientific

↳ Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1903-2021

Topographical Context

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

Notes: Heliopolis includes a number of structures that were built over several periods during Egypt's history. The remains of temple pavement and foundations are still present in a number of areas. For example, in area "200", in the western periphery, the so-called "Suq el-Khamis", is the Temple of Ramesses II. The mud brick enclosure walls are still in place as well. In the centre of the temenos, some features of the facade of the Atum temple of Nektanebo I (380-363 BCE) are still in situ - for example

the threshold of the gate, and part of the soubassement made of decorated basalt slabs. There are also considerable mud brick remains of structures from the temple of the 1st millennium BCE, namely the workshops of the 26th Dynasty, silos, and more. These are concentrated closer to the southern temple enclosure while the stone structures are concentrated in the main processional axis running east-west.

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

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↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:
– Yes [specify]: Creator God (Atum) and Sun god (Ra)

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:
– Yes [specify]: Several

– Yes

Notes: The unique feature of the site, the obelisks, connect the temple to the divine sphere. For instance, offerings could be made on offering tables before the obelisks. This helped connect with the different forms of the solar god, to whom the temple was particularly dedicated, but there were also special Heliopolitan cults for the goddess Hathor (Nebethetepet) and also Osiris (-Sepa) had cults in the 3rd millennium BCE.

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:
– Yes [specify]: Creator God (Atum) and Sun god (Ra)

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:
– Yes [specify]: Several

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Yes

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:
– Yes
Notes: the cult of the royal dynasties

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Yes

↳ Specify
– Revealed by high god

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Birthplace of high god

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Other [specify]: Creation of the world

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– Yes

Notes: We are fairly positive that the "house of life" of Heliopolis (the part of the temple where religious texts were kept) held an important collection of medical texts, which the high priest Khuy himself wrote, dating probably to the later Middle Kingdom. Other texts that were probably stored here also include royal annals. The most important texts that would be expected are solar hymns and cosmographic texts, but these are all lost because of the soil humidity. Texts from other sites reference the "initiated to the secrets of heaven-earth-neverworld of Heliopolis" which seems to refer to such cosmographic knowledge; the voyage of Plato and Eratosthenes in 4th century BCE is said by Strabo to have been aimed at such text collections.

↳ What type of scriptures/sacred texts [specify]:

– Type: Sacred texts and temple archives

↳ Are the scriptures actively used at the place:

– Yes

↳ Are they read aloud:

– Yes

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: Gezirah (hill of sand)

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Sand

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Clay

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Wood

– I don't know

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Notes: The used stones are all from Egypt but from different sites (Aswan, Gebel el-Ahmar, Turah, Abu Zabel and others)

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: mudbricks

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

Notes: There are many small fragments of decoration that have been found that show regular cult activities such as daily offerings and libations, etc. Few of these are full scenes, though it may be possible to reconstruct scenes from the fragments in the future. A few of the larger fragments from the Ramesside Period show the king making libations for the gods Horus and Seth. Some of the foundation reliefs of Nektanebo I show geographic processions of the nomes of Upper Egypt, Lower Egypt and a number of additional pehu-nomes.

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– No

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– No

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

- ↳ Is it writing/caligraphy
 - Yes
- ↳ Are there statues present:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Cult statues:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Statues of humans:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are there paintings present:
 - No
- ↳ Are there mosaics present:
 - No
- ↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other type of decoration:
 - Yes [specify]: friezes of cobras and falcons

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– Yes

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s):

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deified human:

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

↳ Valuable/precious items:

– Yes

↳ Significant value:

Gold, jade, intensely worked objects, or meaningful symbolic value

– Yes

↳ Some value, valuable or useful objects:

– Yes

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– Yes

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– Yes

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: In Egypt, the supreme divine unit was referred to as the Ennead. This was made up of the creator god Atum, with his twin children Schu (air) and heat (Tefnut) as the first emanation of creation. They created the next generation - Osiris - Isis - Seth - Nephthys - which are considered to be part of this cosmological constellation. The most important gods of Heliopolis - are actually the three aspects of the sun - Khepri (in the morning), Ra-Horakhty (at noon), and Atum (in the evening), which of course includes the first elements of creation. Besides this main constellation, there existed a heliopolitan form of Hathor (Nebethetepet) and Horus (Khenti-peru, the ruler of the domains).

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ Are they sky deity:

– Yes

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– Yes

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– Yes

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– Yes

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– Yes

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– Yes

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– No

↳ Are they other:

– Other [specify]: several

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

- ↳ Only through monarch:
 - No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

- ↳ Human spirits can be seen:
 - No

- ↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:
 - I don't know

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

- ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes

- ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes

- ↳ In trance possession:
 - No

- ↳ Through divination practices:
 - Yes

- ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - Yes

- ↳ Only through monarch:
 - No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Yes

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↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be seen:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Yes

↳ Is the cult statue visible:

– No

↳ Is the cult statue hidden:

– Yes

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– Yes

↳ Libations:

– Yes [specify]: Water

↳ Offerings of food:

– Yes [specify]: Bread, beer, wine, beef, poultry

↳ Animal sacrifice:

– Yes [specify]: cattle

↳ Human sacrifice:

– No

↳ Sacred objects:

– Yes [specify]: emblems

↳ Daily life objects:

– Yes [specify]: votives

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Yes

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal sacrifices:

– Yes [specify]: cattle, poultry

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– No

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– Yes

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

↳ By all the community

– No

↳ By specific individuals

– Yes [specify]: priesthood and king

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– No

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– Yes

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

– Field doesn't know

Are festivals present:

– Yes

Notes: Besides regular offering rights, there was an emphasis on lunar festivals with related offerings. Inscriptions from the 19th Dynasty in Karnak claim that the rites completed there were based on those at Heliopolis. An important festival was the feast of the Isched-tree that was celebrated in the course of the coronation ceremonies - the name of the king was expected to appear on the leaves of that tree, written by the god's hand himself. The jubilees of the king also took place in Heliopolis.

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– All members

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– No

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– Field doesn't know

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Yes

↳ Divination by examination of the exta:

Animals remains, internal organs, answer this question and subsequent question once for each species

– No

↳ Divination through human communication:

– Yes

↳ Is a human being the vehicle for the oracle:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is a human being the interpreter of the oracle:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the oracle interpreters of a specified sex/gender:

– No

↳ Are the oracle interpreters of a specified ethnicity:

– No

↳ Are the oracle interpreters of a specified class:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is sex-deprivation required:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are intoxicants required:

– No

↳ Physical ordeal required:

– No

↳ Divination through animal-behavior:

– Yes

↳ Wild-animals

– No

↳ Domesticated animals
– Yes

↳ Captive animals
– Field doesn't know

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Yes

↳ Incubation
– Field doesn't know

↳ Healing magic
– Yes

↳ Cleansing
– Yes

↳ Offerings of models of body parts:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Expiation
– Field doesn't know

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:
– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:
– Yes

↳ How often do these rituals take place:
– specify: daily

- ↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
 - No
- ↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
 - No
- ↳ Are there synchronic practices:
 - No
- ↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:
 - No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

- ↳ Present full time
 - Yes
- ↳ Present part time
 - Yes
- ↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:
 - No
- ↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:
 - No
- ↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– Yes

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Yes

Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Yes

Does this place lease out land:

– Yes

- ↳ Does this place lease out tools:
 - Field doesn't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

- ↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:
 - Yes

- ↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):
 - No

- ↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):
 - Yes

- ↳ Function for water management:
 - No

- ↳ Part of the transportation network:
 - Yes

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

- ↳ Are they written:
 - Yes

- ↳ Are they written at this place:
 - Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– Yes

↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– Yes

↳ Attached to the structures as decoration:

– Yes

↳ Housed within the place/structure:

– Yes

↳ As dedicatory inscription(s):

– Yes

Bibliography

General References

Reference: William Petrie Matthew Flinders, Ernest Mackay. Heliopolis, Kafr Ammar and Shurafa. British School of Archaeology in Egypt and Egyptian Research Account. London: School of Archaeology in Egypt. Bernard Quaritch.

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Reference: Aiman Ashmawy , Dietze Klara , Raue Dietrich. Heliopolis: Kultzentrum unter Kairo. Kleine Schriften des Ägyptischen Museums der Universität Leipzig. Heidelberg: Propylaeum. isbn: 987-3-969-29-002-6.

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